

Mental Health Literacy of College Students in the Post-Pandemic Era

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Abstract:

Mental Health Literacy (MHL) is individuals' knowledge of mental health status, problems, and issues. It includes how people manage, recognize, and prevent mental health problems particularly college students in the post-pandemic era, where unexpected changes occurred. The pandemic and its changes affect people financially, physically, emotionally, and mentally. This study aimed to determine the MHL level of Bachelor of Elementary Education Students enrolled at Mandaue City College in the Post-Pandemic era. The design of this study was a quantitative descriptive design to determine the mental health literacy of college students in the post-pandemic era. The tool used in this study was adapted from O'Connor & Casey's (2019) Mental Health Literacy Scale. Based on the findings, researchers determined that the mental health literacy of college students are capable of recognizing mental health disorders however they are not ready to acknowledge their occurrence. This study implied that college students were aware and knowledgeable enough to professional help available in terms of mental health issues. They can recognize disorders, and in line with this study college students need attention of the health professionals to prevent negative thoughts about their behavior. Furthermore, this study confirmed of Philippine Mental Health Act and Basic Education Mental Health and Well-Being Promotion Act which presents the prevention by giving college students the resources and help they need to improve their mental health and well-being. This theory suggested that there were diverse methods in accessing information that were needed to properly communicate and interact with other people, in a way that they would not feel anxious, and learn to entertain people with confidence.

Keywords: Mental health, college students, MHL, knowledge, Literacy, study, people

Introduction:

Filipinos were known to be optimistic and enthusiastic despite struggles, problems, and pain given by life. However, this joyous reinforcement in today's generation was less as there was an increased number of mental health issues, as conveyed by the World Health Organization (WHO) students or adolescents committing suicide or depression. It was the moment where mental health literacy was much needed. Mental Health Literacy (MHL) is the knowledge regarding mental health status, problems, and issues. It was how they manage, recognize, and prevent mental health problems from occurring (Nejatian, Tehrani, Momeniyan, et al. 2021). Mental health literacy of college students in the post-pandemic era was necessary when unexpected changes happened quickly. The pandemic significant changes affected people financially, physically, emotionally, and mentally. People were forced involuntarily to stay at their homes, transfer work from the workplace to their homes, and were not allowed to go out if not necessary. It prevents people from public interaction and makes people alone as individuals are isolated from one another. Everything became limited and restricted.

The researchers have observed that Mandaue City College (MCC) encourages mental health awareness for several reasons. First of all, it aids in comprehending the unique mental health difficulties that students at the institution encounter. This information makes it possible to create customized interventions and support systems that successfully deal with these particular difficulties. Furthermore, raising awareness of mental health issues fosters a community of support where students feel at ease asking for assistance and acknowledging their own needs. It helps de-stigmatize conversations about mental health and promotes an accepting and supportive environment. Last but not least, funding

mental health research showed MCC's dedication to the overall well-being of its students and promoted a welcoming and supportive learning environment for all. According to the given data by the Guidance counselor in MCC, there were a total of 37 students from 2022 to the present who consulted about their mental health status 10 of them were from the School of Education, five were from the School of Business, three from School of Technology and there were 19 students that have not distinguished as to what school they belong. These numbers may be little from the total population of MCC students, but we can see an after-effect of the pandemic.

However, Filipinos mental health literacy has still been left uninvestigated and given fewer recognition in the field of research. Studies in recent years was fixated only on mental health itself, and there were merely limited studies regarding mental health literacy and its association with Filipinos. Restrictions on collected works examining Filipino college students' mental health literacy showed an opportunity to explore this subject further. It could be for several reasons, including a lack of resources, time, or a change in priorities during the recovery period. Nevertheless, despite these difficulties, MCC needs to comprehend students' post-pandemic experiences to properly customize its support systems, handle any new problems that may arise, and guarantee the well-being of its student body in these changing times. Such research can yield important information for focused assistance and interventions in the post-pandemic educational environment. This gap can be closed by implementing specialized mental health literacy initiatives, seminar services, peer knowledge support groups, or awareness campaigns. Promoting mental health services and encouraging candid communication can have a significant result on mental and general health.

Literature Review:

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 586 million people, suffer from mental illness. Approximately 10-20 percent of young people have mental health problems that affect their performance and can cause educational problems. Ability to recognize specific disorders, know where to find mental health information, recognize potential causes, and be aware. Professional support available for self-help care and self-motivated behaviors to identify and seek appropriate help are all considered components of mental health literacy (MHL). That's why understanding mental health literacy or being mentally ill, is more important than ever. MHL is considered to be a good indicator of health. Mental Health Literacy (MHL) refers to "knowledge and beliefs about mental health conditions that help recognize, manage, and prevent them" and "the ability to recognize specific disorders; skills in finding information about mental health; knowledge of possible causes; personal care and professional help encourage recognition and appropriate help-seeking" (Jorm et al. 1997, adopted and used by P.S Wang et al 2007). The MHL program could be developed using results from a study examining MHL differences between public and private university students. Recovery from mental illness can be delayed due to ignorance and lack of awareness. Families may also in some cases associate mental illness symptoms with spiritual factors, which may encourage relatives to seek help from priests or healers (Kayrouz et al., 2015). The definition of mental health is also a focus of current literature and relates to help-seeking. Knowledge and beliefs that helped recognize, manage, or prevent mental illness were the definition of mental health. People who experience symptoms of psychological disability or who have close ties to others with similar problems will struggle to cope with these symptoms, these symptom management exercises can lead to a reduction in disabling symptoms and a change in perception of mental health. This concept was very important because it focuses on empowering the person showing signs of disability and improving general (as opposed to professional) knowledge and skills related to mental health.

Ability to recognize disorder

One of the biggest barriers to mental health care among students is a lack of awareness of available options on campus. Additionally, one-third of college students were unaware that institutional resources such as counseling and support were offered. Students report poor mental health and inadequate treatment, despite using counseling services more than ever recently. It was difficult for students to ask for help when they were unaware of available resources. It was important to raise awareness about mental health and identify students who may face mental health-related problems. Efforts to prevent and raise awareness of mental health can require help and encourage people to take action when they need it. Raising awareness through campaigns can be a way to help reduce the stigma surrounding mental health. Every year, many institutions organize mental health awareness weeks to promote mental health education.

Knowledge of risk factors and causes

Filipinos believe that mental health problems result from being cursed or possessed by spirits (Tan, 2008), loss of balance and excessive stress (Becker, 2003), having a weak personality, and not receiving adequate support (Thompson et al., 2002) and make it easy to talk about. Mental health literacy includes "knowledge and beliefs about mental health conditions that help identify, manage, and prevent them" as well as "the ability to recognize specific disorders; mental health skills; knowledge of the mind and reason; medical and available professional help, ability to recognize and seek appropriate help." encourages" (I agree with Jorm et al., 1997, and also used by P.S. Wang et al. 2007). Recovery from mental health problems can be delayed due to ignorance and lack of awareness. Families may also in some cases associate mental illness symptoms with spiritual resources, which may encourage family members to seek help from religious leaders or faith healers (Kayrouz et al., 2015). Recent research has also focused on the definition and relationships of mental health and help-seeking. Early intervention programs can be based on the early detection of

mental illnesses made possible by mental health literacy (Tay et al. 2012). , 2018). Appropriate help-seeking behavior has also been encouraged by acceptance of mental illness (Wright et al., 2007).

Knowledge of self-treatment

This concept has the advantage of examining culture and the individual, as these factors are useful in determining how a person wishes to be treated as well as issues related to their mental health. Ethnic and racial factors are also taken into account. Although the mental health model is conceptually useful, the model accounts for broader factors such as socio-economic status (SES), gender roles, social differences, culture and ethnicity (Cauce et al., 2002). The aim was to achieve adolescent development; it was clear that the youth and students in this study could benefit from the same ideas. The model provides a hierarchy that explains how a person can proceed through the help-seeking process, starting with recognizing that they have a problem, deciding to seek help, and ending with choosing a treatment method (Cauce et al. 2012). Each category within this category can be influenced by circumstances and culture. For example, a person's culture can influence what or behavior is considered mental health. Additionally, while in some cases mental health behaviors or symptoms may be acceptable and taken for granted, in other cases this may not be the case Tulu et al.

Knowledge of professional health available

Their performance can cause problems in their schools (WHO, 2020). Due to the prevalence of stress among students, attention is paid to students' mental health (Kirsh et al., 2015). According to academic institutions, the number of students receiving mental health care and the severity of their symptoms have increased (Castillo and Schwartz, 2013; Lipson et al., 2016). Mental health policies should prioritize the solution of health problems among young people (Çuhadaroğlu, 2018; Hofman and Mühlenweg, 2018). However, thoughts about mental health are shifting in a positive direction, with greater emphasis on creating healthy habits and behaviors (Aldridge and McChesney, 2018; Barry et al., 2013). Young people are more likely to seek help if they can recognize symptoms and understand mental health problems (Gulliver et al., 2010).

Knowledge where to seek information

According to mental health literacy and intervention literature, a students' knowledge of mental health concerns may be influenced by a variety of factors. There is a strong connection between mental health education and completing a psychology course, studying psychology, or entering the counseling profession (Lumaksono et al., 2020; Miles et al., 2020). Improvements in mental health services were also observed among students who previously had mental health problems, were diagnosed, and/or treated (Dahlberg et al. 2014). 2008; Lauber et al., 2005; Miles et al., 2020). Students who talked openly about mental health with their families or had face-to-face contact with a friend or family member with mental illness also showed an increase in mental health advocacy (Miles et al., 2020; Reavley et al. 2020). , 2014). A comprehensive research review was conducted to determine the effectiveness of programs aimed at improving mental health and mental health. All articles in the meta-analysis included adults, and most of them were mostly college students. Overall, the activity improved mental health and literacy (Brijnath et al., 2016; Davies et al., 2016).

Attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior

Every student faces stress and anxiety, which can be difficult to manage and can worsen pre-existing mental health problems. Students with low mental health knowledge may isolate themselves or resort to coping mechanisms because they are not aware of resources to support those (Kutcher et al., 2016). Students in classrooms not exposed to emotional literacy or mental health issues may find this difficult (Lauber et al., 2005; Miles et al., 2020). Therefore, it is important to look at these unhelpful student characteristics to determine the need for interventions to increase knowledge and understanding of mental health issues. Research (Rafal et al., 2018; Cheng et al., 2018) has shown that inadequate mental literacy can be a significant barrier that prevents youth and students from receiving mental health services. Additionally, studies have indicated that young people's awareness of the advantages of mental health care is a good indicator of whether or not they will ask for assistance (O'Connor et al., 2014). More importantly, this episode can be used to introduce and educate people about mental health and available treatments. This shows that it is important to find ways to improve mental health knowledge because this will actually benefit people's health. The mental health and well-being of young adults is so poor that it should be considered a public health problem.

Research Method:

In this study, a quantitative research methodology with a descriptive design was utilized to assess college students' mental health literacy in the post-pandemic era. Adedoyin (2020) defines quantitative research as the study of phenomena by numerical data and statistical, analytical, or computational instruments. The respondents of this research study were all Bachelor of Elementary Education majors in General Content who were officially enrolled in Mandaue City College. The Instrument used was the Mental Health Literacy Skills (MHLS) a 35-item scale-based assessment of an individual's mental health literacy level (O'Conner & Casey, 2015). The scale evaluates the capacity to recognize disorders, awareness of where to get information, understanding of risk factors and causes, knowledge of self-treatment, knowledge of available professional help, and attitudes that encourage recognition or appropriate help-seeking actions. MHLS was validated in the Filipino context and found that four out of six subscales of MHLS were reliable ($\alpha = .852, .800,$

.867, .896) and the remaining two subscales had low consistency ($\alpha = .366$ and $.347$). Despite that, the overall Cronbach Alpha was 0.780 which makes the questionnaire considered to be reliable.

Findings and Discussion:

Grounded on the results of the study, students of Mandaue City College can recognize mental health disorders, they are knowledgeable about how to deal with it and they knew of its existence but were disquieted to acknowledge it. The ability to recognize disorder is the capacity of a person to know whether a type of mental disorder has occurred or has been experienced. It shows self-awareness of what is happening to one's mental situation.

Table 1
Ability to Recognize Disorder

<i>Ability to Recognize Disorder</i>	INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
	If someone became extremely nervous or anxious in one or more situations with other people (e.g., a party) or performance situations (e.g., presenting at a meeting) in which they were afraid of being evaluated by others and that they would act in a way that was humiliating or feel embarrassed, then to what extent do you think it is likely they have Social Phobia.	3.03	Likely
	To what extent do you think it is likely that Persistent Depressive Disorder is a disorder	3.01	Likely
	If someone experienced a low mood for two or more weeks, had a loss of pleasure or interest in their normal activities and experienced changes in their appetite and sleep then to what extent do you think it is likely they have Major Depressive Disorder	3.00	Likely
	If someone experiences excessive worry about a number of events or activities where this level of concern was not warranted, had difficulty controlling this worry and had physical symptoms such as having tense muscles and feeling fatigued then to what extent do you think it is likely they have Generalized Anxiety Disorder.	2.97	Likely
	To what extent do you think it is likely that the diagnosis of Bipolar Disorder includes experiencing periods of elevated (i.e., high) and periods of depressed (i.e., low) mood.	2.96	Likely
	To what extent do you think it is likely that the diagnosis of Substance Abuse Disorder includes physical and psychological tolerance of the drug (i.e., require more of the drug to get the same effect).	2.96	Likely
	To what extent do you think it is likely that in general in the Philippines, women are MORE likely to experience a mental illness of any kind compared to men.	2.94	Likely
	To what extent do you think it is likely that Personality Disorders are a category of mental illness.	2.93	Likely
	To what extent do you think it is likely that the diagnosis of Agoraphobia includes anxiety about situations where escape may be difficult or embarrassing.	2.87	Likely
	To what extent do you think it is likely that in general, in Philippines, men are MORE likely to experience an anxiety disorder compared to women.	2.68	Likely
	Total	2.94	Likely

Table 1 showed that most of the students in MCC were likely to recognize disorder, as the highest indicators showed that students of MCC were likely to have a social phobia and feel nervous in situations that would make them communicate or socialize with others. When they were with a crowd that would negatively evaluate them on how well they do their schoolwork they feel anxious. World Health Organization (WHO) states that social anxiety disorder is one of the most serious mental illnesses as it affects the everyday communication and connection between humans. Social Phobia may be recognizable yet, it was not easy to overcome. It limits one's capabilities to express and share ideas (Melkam et al. Systematic Reviews) (2023). It presented that social phobia was easy to recognize but difficult to solve. It was an issue in connecting to people, people that do not give the feeling of security to people to act as they are. It limits not just for them to connect but also to communicate with them.

Knowledge of risk factors and causes covers a wide range of topics, such as mental health. Risk factors have been found to have an impact on student performance. This means that students should prioritize their mental well-being than emphasizing their mental health problems.

Table 2:
Knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes

<i>Knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes</i> INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
To what extent do you think it would be helpful for someone to avoid all activities or situations that made them feel anxious if they were having difficulties managing their emotions.	2.96	Likely
To what extent do you think it would be helpful for someone to improve their quality of sleep if they were having difficulties managing their emotions (e.g., becoming very anxious or depressed).	2.95	Likely
Total	2.96	Likely

The result agreed that, among teenagers or college students, having difficulties handling their emotions was the most common mental health issue. Though, the coping mechanisms they employ to overcome these challenges and take control of their emotions. This implied that college students should focus on their personal recovery and emphasize that was better to live a meaningful life. It would be beneficial for someone to stay away from the situations that makes them feel anxious to reduce stress. This agreed with Oosterhooff et al., 2020; Racine et al., 2021. WHO 2020. To reduce mental health issues or negative behavior social isolation and school closure have a big impact on improving and protecting mental health especially in college students. It will be helpful for college students to avoid activities that can triggered the mental health or negative behavior of every students in MCC. It stated that it would also be helpful if college students improve their quality of sleep despites of any circumstances.

This implied that there might be a connection between knowledge of mental health difficulties and the willingness to seek proper treatment, as people with better mental health literacy may have more positive views toward obtaining professional help.

Table 3
Knowledge of Self-Treatment

<i>Knowledge of Self-Treatment</i> INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
To what extent do you think it is likely that Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT) is a therapy based on challenging negative thoughts and increasing helpful behaviours.	3.01	Likely
Mental health professionals are bound by confidentiality; however there are certain conditions under which this does not apply. To what extent do you think it is likely that the following is a condition that would allow a mental health professional to break confidentiality: <i>If you are at immediate risk of harm to yourself or others</i>	3.00	Likely
Mental health professionals are bound by confidentiality; however there are certain conditions under which this does not apply. To what extent do you think it is likely that the following is a condition that would allow a mental health professional to break confidentiality: <i>if your problem is not life-threatening and they want to assist others to better support you</i>	2.89	Likely
Total	2.97	Likely

Legend: 1:00-1:75 (Very Unlikely); 1:76-2:50 (Unlikely); 2:51-3:25 (Likely); 3:26-4:00 (Very Unlikely)

Table 3 shown the result of this study on mental health among students in the post-pandemic era, which means that every professional is bound by confidentiality but there were certain conditions under which this does not apply so professionals break the rules to protect the mental health of the student and give the needs and attention to prevent

negative thoughts about student’s behavior. This table implied that there were some mental health issues of college students that professionals can break the confidentiality of their professions to protect and to prevent the negative behavior of the students.

Table 4:
Knowledge of Professional Help Available
Knowledge of Professional Help Available

INDICATORS	Weighted	Descriptive
	Mean	Equivalent
I am confident I have access to resources (e.g., GP, internet, friends) that I can use to seek information about mental illness	3.06	Likely
I am confident that I know where to seek information about in mental illness.	2.97	Likely
I am confident using the computer or telephone to seek information about mental illness	2.94	Likely
Total	2.99	Likely

Legend: 1:00-1:75 (Very Unlikely); 1:76-2:50 (Unlikely); 2:51-3:25 (Likely); 3:26-4:00 (Very Unlikely)

This study suggested that the majority of students are open to the idea of using the internet to find knowledge of healthcare utilization and online health information was becoming more and more obvious as consumers of health care become more and more reliant on the internet. The result agreed with the study of Ybarra & Suman (2006) cited by which states that seekers of medical care seem to be utilizing the Internet to improve their access to care; they report diagnosing issues with the use of online resources and reporting feeling more confident in their health provider's advice as a result. Research shows that those who look up health information online are more likely to be concerned about their health; some websites that provide mental health information have been shown in recent studies to enhance mental well-being and lessen depressive symptoms.

Table 5:
Knowledge of where to seek information

INDICATORS	Weighted	Descriptive
	Mean	Equivalent
People with a mental illness could snap out of it if they wanted.	3.01	Likely
A mental illness is not a real medical illness	2.74	Likely
A mental illness is a sign of personal weakness	2.66	Likely
People with a mental illness are dangerous	2.49	Unlikely
Seeing a mental health professional means you are not strong enough to manage your own difficulties.	2.11	Unlikely
If I had a mental illness, I would not tell anyone.	2.00	Unlikely
It is best to avoid people with a mental illness so that you don't develop this problem	2.01	Unlikely
If I had a mental illness, I would not seek help from a mental health professional.	1.82	Unlikely
I believe treatment for a mental illness, provided by a mental health professional, would not be effective	1.76	Unlikely
Total	2.29	Unlikely

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Very Unlikely); 1.76-2.50 (Unlikely); 2.51-3.25 (Likely); 3.26-4.00 (Very Likely)

Student’s mental health literacy incorporates knowledge of where to seek information, discover up-to-date data almost mental wellbeing conditions, treatment and back assets. This may incorporate websites, scholarly databases, and meetings with mental wellbeing experts, all of whom can give definitive direction in tending to the mental wellbeing needs of individual or adored ones.

Overall, college students are more mentally literate when it comes to knowing where to look for information and are aware that getting professional assistance is usually the best course of action when handling mental health problems. The significance of obtaining professional assistance for mental health issues is supported by a literature review conducted by Gabriel et al. (2021), since it can result in an early diagnosis and treatment. For mental health illnesses to be effectively managed and recovered from, early intervention was essential. A specialist in mental health can offer a thorough assessment, identify the ailment, and create a customized treatment strategy. This may lessen symptoms and enhance mental wellness in general. Better Mental Health and well-being. College students’ overall and mental welfare can significantly improve with the help of a professional. A mental health professional can provide information on treatment options, teach relaxation techniques, stress management strategies, and improve communication skills to manage symptoms and strengthen relationships.

Table 6:
Attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior

<i>Attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior</i>		
INDICATORS	Weighted	Descriptive
	Mean	Equivalent
How willing would you be to make friends with someone with mental illness?	2.86	Likely
How willing would you be to move next door to someone with mental illness?	2.83	Likely
How willing would you be to spend an evening socializing with someone with a mental illness?	2.80	Likely
How willing would you be to have someone with a mental illness start working closely with you on a job?	2.72	Likely
How willing would you be to employ someone if you knew they had a mental illness?	2.43	Unlikely
How willing would you be to have someone with mental illness marry into your family?	2.39	Unlikely
How willing would you be to vote for a politician if you knew they had suffered a mental illness?	2.17	Unlikely
Total	2.6	Likely

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Very Unlikely); 1.76-2.50 (Unlikely); 2.51-3.25 (Likely); 3.26-4.00 (Very Likely)

Encouraging people to use mental health services with transparency, empathy, and confidence can help them recognize mental health difficulties and feel empowered to get help from a professional. People may be further motivated to prioritize their mental health if they have positive attitudes about the efficacy of mental health therapies and a sense of communal duty for fostering emotional well-being. Cultivating these positive attitudes is essential to mental health literacy because it helps people overcome stigma and take the correct actions to take care of their mental health needs.

Research results suggested that recognition of mental abnormalities indicated a propensity to suggest or plan to seek assistance from reliable sources, but also linked to a decreased inclination to ask for assistance from any sources such as family and peers (Wright et al. 2012; Yap et al. 2014). In adult populations, comparable results had been stated (Angermeyer et al. 2009; Rusch et al. 2012); But the bulk of these research has been on social phobia, depression, and schizophrenia and related psychoses. Therefore, knowledge about other mental ailments was lacking such as obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). The inability to correctly recognize that mental illnesses can lead to improper help-seeking and treatment delays seeking (Jorm, 2000). Additionally, research has demonstrated that waiting around for suitable

treatment result in negative outcomes, due to longer duration of untreated illness, and consequently, poorer treatment outcomes (Marshall et al. 2005; Altamura et al. 2008, 2010; de Diego-Adeliño et al. 2010). Family members and friends, who often provide essential, people who need assistance and support for mental health issues may also face stigma. Perhaps they internalize the shame and put the responsibility on themselves, or they fear social rejection from others or that they are too responsible for the illness of a loved one. Social marginalization, a lack of emotional support, and a refusal to seek medical help for family members are all consequences of this stigma. The implication from this table could emphasize the importance of recognizing mental health issues, seeking appropriate help, and providing support, especially in environments where stigma and stress may hinder individuals from seeking assistance. It highlights the need for comprehensive research covering various mental ailments to ensure proper understanding and treatment. Additionally, it underscores the impact of leaders' well-being on decision-making processes and the necessity of support systems to help them cope with stress effectively.

Table 7:
Mental Health Literacy Scale

<i>Indicators</i>	Total Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Knowledge of Professional Help Available	2.99	Likely
Knowledge of Self-Treatment	2.97	Likely
Knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes	2.96	Likely
Ability to Recognize Disorder	2.94	Likely
Attitudes that promote recognition or appropriate help-seeking behavior	2.60	Likely
Knowledge of where to seek information	2.29	Unlikely
	Total 2.79	Likely

The results in Table 7 illustrate how the statement relates to students' mental health literacy. The table shows the range of average student mental health literacy skills from the highest to the lowest. Mental health literacy (MHL) is defined as the capacity to identify specific disorders, the know-how to look for information about mental health, the awareness of risk factors and causes, the knowledge of self-care and the resources available to seek professional help, and the attitudes that encourage both identification and appropriate help-seeking. That being said, it is now more crucial than ever to understand mental health literacy, or one's awareness of mental disease.

According to the results of a poll, young people with mental health disorders should receive the following first aid. The results showed that many youngsters did not think seeking professional aid was beneficial. Some parents did not advocate for getting professional assistance because they were not well-versed in mental health issues. Young people with mental health concerns frequently face barriers to getting help, and a systematic study by Gulliver et al. and Radez found that poor mental health literacy was the primary cause of these barriers. Additionally, individuals will not be able to get the right care for their mental health problems if they are unaware of the warning signs of mental sickness. The lack of knowledge about mental health therapies is a significant additional barrier. The lack of knowledge about mental health therapies is a significant additional barrier. Because understanding professional assistance and treatment was a critical part of health literacy or awareness, it was reasonable to infer that persons who knew enough about it also knew enough about mental health. Finding these resources and understanding how they operate is necessary in order to receive mental health therapy.

Conclusion:

Based on the conclusions of the study, researchers determined that MCC students were literate in regards to mental health and knew the factors and causes for it to occur, had the knowledge of ways of self-treatment, and knew professionals were available yet they were not aware where to seek information, they were well informed and knowledgeable of the right attitudes in seeking help from other people. College students were aware and knowledgeable

enough to identify and seek help regarding mental health literacy. And can recognize disorders, in line with this study, college students need attention from health professionals to prevent negative thoughts about their behavior. Furthermore, this study confirmed from Philippine Mental Health Act and Basic Education Mental Health and Well-Being Promotion Act which presents the prevention by giving college student the resources and help they need to improve their mental health. One of the other main aspects of this legislation is the establishment of mental health amenities within schools. It also mandates that mental health and counseling services should be offered in all public and private educational institutions, including colleges and universities. This equips educators with the understanding and capability necessary to recognize, support, and link students who may be facing mental health distresses.

Limitations and Further Research:

Based on the findings regarding the Mental Health Literacy of college students in the Post-Pandemic Era. The following recommendations were made for students, instructors, and student services towards mental health literacy-related activities.

For students, three possible programs are recommended, First, Convey Classroom-Based Mental Health Education, it was possible to lessen stigma and enhance students' understanding and attitudes around mental health by implementing mental health education in the classroom. When students can practice skills and participate in the lesson, it is most beneficial. Then the Lesson Stigma instills a supportive school climate and teaches students to identify and resist stigmatizing attitudes about mental health. Lastly, Peer-led modeling programs, adolescent leaders will be trained to model positive attitudes, abilities, and behaviors through peer-led modeling programs. Healthy coping mechanisms that they can employ and impart to their peers were taught to peer leaders.

For the Instructors, three programs were recommended, Interactive and practical training, which provide training programs with modules that contain information unique to recognizing and assisting pupils who have had hardship or were having psychological issues. Include chances for introspection, discussion, and interactive videos that showcase particular competencies. Then consistent mental health training, to meet the changing essentials of educators and students, provide mental health training throughout pre-service education and regular chances for continuing education. Finally the Collaboration with mental health professionals to ensure evidence-based practices and accurate information by involving mental health experts in the formulation and execution of MHL training. Teachers can improve their MHL and provide better support for the mental health and general health of students by putting these guidelines into practice.

For Student Services, Peer Facilitators or selected students can help enhance mental health literacy in college students or adolescents specifically in mental health promotion and prevention, which is an effective strategy for improving knowledge and seeking help. Then the collaborating Learning and Teaching Methods, the College students' MHL should be improved through the use of collaborative learning and teaching methods to integrate mental health education into awareness-raising campaigns and the provision of tools to enhance mental resilience and avert mental health illnesses can help achieve this goal. Lastly, the provision activities mental health activities was essential if college students were to become more mentally literate. Mindfulness exercises and keeping a regular sleep schedule were examples of self-care activities.

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